

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Economic evaluation of the reduction of phosphate fertilizers and the use of mycorrhiza in potato cultivation in Galicia

Evaluating the economic impact of sustainable agricultural practices is key to determining their feasibility and profitability, as their adoption depends on their ability to maintain or improve profitability compared to conventional methods. This study analyzes the impact of reducing or eliminating phosphate fertilizers in combination with the use of mycorrhizal inoculants on potato production in Galicia during a three-year potato-barley-potato rotation.

Five strategies are compared: (T1) conventional, (T2) 50% reduction of fertilizers, (T3) 50% reduction + mycorrhiza, (T4) no fertilizers, and (T5) no fertilizers + mycorrhiza. The treatments without phosphate fertilizer (with and without mycorrhiza) achieved the highest profitability (23,146 €/ha and 22,777 €/ha, respectively) and surpassing conventional management

(21,894 €/ha). In contrast, a 50% reduction in fertilizer led to a significant decrease in crop yields, indicating that this strategy is not economically advantageous.

Despite the high variability in the data, the results confirm that not using phosphate fertilizers, especially in combination with mycorrhiza, is an economically viable strategy that reduces production costs without compromising potato yields.

This information provides a solid basis for farmers to adopt these practices, which are not only profitable, but also reduce dependence on expensive chemical inputs, protect economic yields from fertilizer price volatility, and improve the long-term sustainability of their crops. It also helps to develop policies based on scientific evidence.

1. Graph showing how gross margins vary according to the different agricultural practices used. It illustrates the overall distribution of the data obtained, including the most frequent values (shaded box), the mean value (black line), and the extreme values (highest and lowest values).

	Costs (€/ha)	Revenue (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
T1: Conventional	13,497	31,599	21,894
T2: 50%	12,931	26,662	16,923
T3: 0%	12,371	31,382	22,777
T4: 50%+Ms	13,338	29,039	19,186
T5: 0%+Ms	12,778	32,075	23,146

2. Average value of production costs, sales revenues, and gross margins, calculated for each practice analysed in a 3-year rotation (potato-barley-potato).

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, phosphate fertilizers, potato cultivation, mycorrhizae

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